

India's growth story: Challenges and Opportunities

*Dr. Archana Kumari **

India's journey towards becoming a developed nation by 2047 captures the ambition, resilience and commitment of India to pursue holistic development across every sector. But in the path of Viksit Bharat India has to tackle major challenges including bridging significant economic and social inequalities, efforts of less unemployment through robust job creation, enhancing infrastructure, reforming governance, ensuring quality education, improving ease of doing business, environmental up gradation, fostering innovation etc. India needs to do a lot across all these sectors. NITI Aayog, the primary driver of the Viksit Bharat initiative, has expressed strong confidence in India's potential to achieve its ambitious goals. This paper explores the challenges and opportunities required to transform this vision into reality creating a future-ready India that leads the world in innovation, equality and sustainability.

Key words: Viksit Bharat, Challenges, Opportunities, Reforms, Vision .

The Vikshit Bharat Abhiyan(Developed India Mission) was ideated by a revered policymaker , prof. Rajendra Pratap Gupta in the book- Rebuilding India in the next 25 years- Tough Choices and Hard Decisions. This abhiyan is drafting a detailed plan for all sectors in order to guide various stakeholders and to prepare Indians for a better tomorrow. The overarching theme of the vikshitbharat@2047 mission is to transform India into a developed nation by 2047, the 100th year of its independence. The vision is built upon the pillars of economic prosperity, social advancement, environmental sustainability and effective governance emphasizing inclusivity, innovation, self-reliance and active participation of youth in nation-building.

Prime Minister Narendra Modi stated that the goal of achieving 'Viksit' (developed) status for India by 2047 could be realized by focusing on GYAN, which stands for Garib (poor), Yuva (youth), Annadata (farmers), and Narishakti (women empowerment). PM Modi's 'Viksit Bharat 2047' initiative aims to transform India into a developed nation. PM Modi emphasizes that "Hum GYAN pe dhyaan denge, GYAN ko sammaan denge, toh Viksit Bharat banega" (If we focus on and respect knowledge, India will become developed). The next 25 years are crucial for the country, and he observes a sense of confidence among the people that India will achieve developed status by the time it celebrates its 100th anniversary of independence¹

Vision of Viksit Bharat 2047

The Vision of Viksit Bharat 2047 is an all-encompassing and ambitious strategy that aims to make India a developed nation by 2047. The Viksit Bharat 2047

* Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, M.R.M College, Lalit Narayan Mithila University, Darbhanga, Bihar.

vision to achieve economic prosperity, infrastructure development, human capital development, innovation, and technology advancement, social inclusion and equity, environmental sustainability, good governance, and institutional strengthening, as well as global leadership and diplomacy. The goal is to elevate India to upper-middle-income status by 2047 by fostering entrepreneurship, attracting investments, and enhancing productivity across sectors. The infrastructure development will include modernizing transportation networks, expanding energy infrastructure, improving urban amenities, and ensuring connectivity in rural areas. Human capital development will focus on education, healthcare, and skill development, promoting lifelong learning and employability. Moreover, Innovation and technological advancement will drive global competitiveness, social inclusion and equity, environmental sustainability, good governance, and global leadership (Patel, V., and Kumar, R. (2024)²

Review of Literature

Jayaprada Sahoo and Dr. Suresh Vadranam (2024)³ discussed on Viksit Bharat @2047 Transformation of Society and they tell about Future Vision and Accomplishments. Government Authorities plays important role for Policy Making and their Implementation And They Also Discuss Economic Growth, Social Progress, Environment Sustainability And Good Governance. Good Education System Resolves Many Problems And Challenges Who Are Hurdles For Becoming Develop Nations. Indian Education System Mainly Focus On Research And Innovations. So, It Can Be Better For Future Goals.

Bhattacharya, Satya Sundar (2023)⁴ these Authors Discuss About Indian Economy Journey Why India Count As A Developing Economy After 75 Years Of Independence. Britisers Empire Times and Their Wealth Movement. Comparison The Situation Of Current Standards And What Steps Taken By Government To Achieved Status Of Develop Nation.

PhD Chamber Of Commerce and Industry (2024)⁵ In this Article, they Discuss About Indian Economy Growth Rate In Past Decades And Expected Size Of The Economy. And History of Per Capita Income, Sectoral Value Added In India GDP. And Also Talk About Factor Who Helps To Becoming Manufacturing Hub. India Also Needs To Improve Ease Of Doing Business Norms And Indicators. Startup Ecosystem, Infrastructure Development Perspectives Research and Development Activities, Dynamics of Exports Education, Skill and Employment Creation They All Factors Helps Occurrence Growth of the Economy.

Objectives of the Study:

The main objectives of this study are to review and identify the vision of the viksit bharat @2047. On this basic he following objectives is set

-) To Analyze the Vision of Viksit Bharat 2047 As Proposed By the Government of India.
-) To evaluate reforms in different sectors needed
-) To assess the strategies, Opportunities and Challenges.

Challenges for Viksit Bharat:-

Per Capita Income- India's per capita income must grow at 7.3% per year in dollar terms, reaching \$14000 in the next 24 years.

Current situation (2023-2024):- India's per capita income is \$2.570 which is very low as compared to developed nations like USA, South Korea and Taiwan.

Target: By 2047-48, India needs to reach \$14000 per capita income, which is the World Bank's threshold for a developed country.

GDP Growth Rate: - India's GDP must grow at 7.9% annually over the next 24 years because the population is expected to grow by 0.6% annually until 2050(according to UN). So, overall GDP must grow faster than per capita income. India's real GDP growth in dollar terms over the last 21 years was 7.8%.

Income and regional inequality, quality education, unemployment, health and infrastructure gap, climate change and environmental degradation, political polarization and administrative bottlenecks, urban congestion and rural underdevelopment etc. are some major challenges which need a lot of attention.

GDP is expected to rise from USD 4.18 trillion (2025) to USD 30 trillion (2047), accompanied by a sustained acceleration in industrial output, services growth, and infrastructure investment. India's urban population is expected to rise from 37% in 2023 to 51% by 2047 and 65% by 2070, implying substantial expansion of existing cities and the emergence of new urban centres. Rising incomes and urbanisation will increase per-capita energy demand through higher mobility requirements, widespread appliance use, cooling needs, and the growth of commercial services.

Government Initiatives for Viksit Bharat

-) Make in India and Aatmanirbhar Bharat: Promote domestic manufacturing and reduce import dependency.
-) PLI Schemes: Financial incentives for key sectors like electronics, pharma, and textiles.
-) PM Gati Shakti Master Plan: Integrates infrastructure projects across sectors for faster development.
-) Digital India: Expands internet access, boosts fintech adoption, and supports e-governance.
-) National Education Policy (NEP 2020): Reforms in education to create a skilled workforce.
-) Green India Mission: Focus on renewable energy and sustainable urban development.

Strategies for Viksit Bharat

India has huge potential:-

-) Low- income countries tend to grow faster than high income ones when they implement the right policies. Example- South Korea and China experienced rapid economic growth when they were at India's current situation.
-) If a country has low per capita income, it had more potential for faster growth by adopting existing technologies, skill and capital investments.

J .Developed countries like the US and Germany grow slowly (1-3%) because they are already at a high income level.

Factors that will help India to achieve this Growth:

Develop new technology and improve existing technology

Example- South Korea used Japanese and Western technologies in manufacturing to grow rapidly. India can do the same by improving its use of AI, automation and industrial production.

Capital Accumulation (investment in industries):- More factories, business and industries have to be set up which creates more jobs and higher income.

India needs to attract domestic and foreign investments in manufacturing, infrastructure and technology.

Skill Acquisition (better education and Workforce training):- To sustain high growth, India must improve the skills of its Workforce. Investing in education, vocational training and higher education will help India move towards a high- productivity economy.

Reforms Needed

Focus on Labour- Intensive Industries:- Textiles and garment industry is one of the most labour intensive sectors globally.

Example- Bangladesh has rapidly expanded its textile industry; providing millions of jobs. India already has an advantage with a large pool of low cost labor and policies like the PLI (Production Linked Incentive) scheme for textiles are steps in the right direction.

Manufacturing: - Manufacturing (especially low-end electronics, consumer goods, furniture etc.) can absorb a significant number of workers.

Example- China has created millions of jobs in manufacturing by becoming the World's factory. India can similarly build out mass manufacturing sectors like automobiles, electronics and consumer appliances.

Governance and Economic Reforms

Strengthening Governance and Improved Public Administration: - India needs efficient Governance structure to ensure the smooth implementation of policies.

Example: - In South Korea the government's efficient bureaucratic system helped rapidly implement industrial policies and create jobs.

.Ease of doing business: - The business climate must be more conducive to Startups, SMEs (Small and medium enterprises) and foreign investments.

Example- India has improved in global ratings for ease of doing business but taxation, labor laws and regulatory complexities still pose challenges.

Digital Governance: - Digitalization of government services (e.g .e- governance) is key to improving transparency and efficiency.

Example- Estonia, a small country has successfully implemented digital Governance with e- residency, e- voting and other services, making Governance much more efficient and transparent. India can take inspiration from such models.

Technology Reforms

- Invest in AI & Emerging Technologies: Expand India's domestic AI ecosystem by building robust public compute infrastructure, chip fabrication facilities, and a sovereign cloud to ensure technological self-reliance and global competitiveness
- Digital Rights & Consumer Protection: Swiftly implement Digital Personal Data Protection (DPDP) Act, 2023 to give users control over data, hold companies accountable, and enable secure data transfer, ensuring privacy and trust.
- Education & Skills for the Future: Integrate ethics, arts, climate, and digital civics into STEM to nurture critical thinking and responsible innovation.
- Audits & Ethics in Technology: Mandate Tech Impact Assessments for start-ups and implement [ethical and explainable AI law](#) with bias checks, data consent, and transparency.
- Security, Crypto & Innovation: India needs a modern cyber security framework ready to tackle future AI led cyber warfare.
- India must set clear [crypto rules](#) on taxation, compliance, and consumer protection to boost innovation and global digital economy integration.

Economic Reforms: - Capital market reforms- To support higher growth, India needs more efficient markets that allows business to access funds easily.

Example- Countries like South Korea and China have strong stocks market and financial systems that support industrial growth and expansion.

India has made progress with initiatives like corporate bond markets and the National Infrastructure Investment Fund (NIIF) but more reforms are needed.

Land and Infrastructure Reforms: - Reforms in the land acquisition process are critical for industrialization, especially in sectors like manufacturing and real estate.

Example: Vietnam has streamlined its land acquisition process which has helped its manufacturing sector boom.

- Transport Modernisation: Future rail mobility requires investments in Hyperloop, bullet, and driverless trains, with policy reforms for fare rationalization and private investment, while maintaining affordability.
- Public transport needs efficient bus, rapid rail, and monorail systems and last-mile connectivity to improve state services.
- Regulate & Rationalise: Promote [green freight](#) with multimodal hubs and electric trucks for low-carbon logistics.
- Introduce single-window vehicle clearances for manufacturing, emissions, and safety approvals.
- Infrastructure Indexing: Create a public district-level infrastructure dashboard tracking health, education, transport, civic amenities, and digital assets to guide policy and ensure equitable development.
- Ports & Logistics: About 95% of India's trade by volume and 65% by value moves through maritime transport.

- As India pursues its ambitious target of 10,000 Million Tonnes Per Annum (MTPA) port capacity by 2047, it requires the development of world-class ports, digitized cargo systems, green freight solutions, and efficient logistics hubs.

Agriculture Reforms

- **Finance & Fertility:** Improve farm credit access. Replace input subsidies with direct cash transfers. Boost fertility via irrigation, mechanisation, climate-resilient seed varieties, and climate-smart farming.
- India can reduce 6–12% post-harvest losses by investing in cold storage at farms and mandis.
- **Agri Markets & Export:** Expand [APMC \(Agricultural Produce Market Committee\)](#) coverage, allow private procurement and contract farming.
- India can boost agricultural exports to USD 70 billion by focusing on value chains for high-potential items like rice, spices, fruits, and vegetables.
- **Rural Livelihoods:** Promote dairying, poultry, fishing, and beekeeping to diversify incomes.

India should actively pursue an ethanol blending programme to boost farmers' income, making them 'Urjadata' alongside 'Annadata.'

However, India must balance food and energy security, as 20% ethanol blending diverts grains and sugarcane, risking food shortages.'

Market & Land Security: Replace [MSP \(Minimum Support Price\)](#) with comprehensive insurance covering market prices & disasters.

Ensure clear land ownership titles via digitalisation and integrate block chain in [Digital India Land Records Modernization Programme \(DILRMP\)](#).

Education Reforms

- **Literacy & Learning:** India needs to spend 6% of GDP on public education, focus on foundational skills, teacher training, and accountability.
- **Education Regulation:** Strengthen higher education regulators like the University Grants Commission and All India Council for Technical Education to reduce administrative burdens, allowing institutions to focus on quality, research, and innovation.
- **Acquire Skills Early:** Integrate vocational training in schools to bridge the gap between academics and industry needs.
- **Reach Global Standards:** Invite top foreign universities, aim for an Indian university in the global top 100, and improve sports infrastructure in schools.
- **Nurture Innovation & Digital Learning:** Digitize curricula, leverage tech in classrooms, encourage private capital in universities, and reform testing mechanisms supported by initiatives like [PARAKH](#).

Health Reforms

- **Coverage & Care:** Guarantee Right to Health with a Universal Health Coverage under [Ayushman Bharat Yojana](#).
- **Unified Standards:** Mandate hospital accreditation and enforce clear labelling of health products for quality, safety, and affordability.

- Records & Rights: Under the [Ayushman Bharat Health Account \(ABHA\)](#), ensure health data ownership, explicit patient consent, digital security, and strong oversight for personal health information.
- Encourage Innovation: Promote domestic Med Tech start-ups, support early-stage innovations, and create a national trauma care grid for emergency response.

Environment & Sustainability Reforms

- Green Manufacturing & Hydrogen: Mandate eco-friendly industrial practices, promote [green hydrogen](#) adoption, and decarbonise key sectors like steel, cement, and metals.
- Renewable Energy & Battery R&D: Expand [renewable energy capacity](#), invest in future battery technology, and reduce dependence on imports for energy storage.
- Emissions & Carbon Trading: Develop structured [carbon markets](#), voluntary crediting mechanisms, and policies to prevent double counting and fraud.
- Environmental Protection & Waste Management: Tackle air pollution by improving district-wise monitoring.
- Promote recycling, [e-waste management](#), and create marketplaces for recyclable waste.
- Nature & Climate-Resilient Urban Planning: Under the [Smart Cities Mission](#), plan climate-resilient cities as beacons of India's Green Transition by incentivizing sustainable urban development and linking grants for municipalities to cleanliness and renewable energy adoption.

Tax Reforms: - India's tax system should continue evolving to make it simpler more transport and better at encouraging investment and job creation.

Example: The GST was a major step forward, but further simplification and tax compliance improvements are still needed.

Conclusion:- Viksit Bharat 2047 is the government's vision to drive the mission of making India a completely developed nation by its 100th anniversary of independence in 2047. "Bold Vision, Brighter Future" is more than a slogan –it is defining the roadmap for a Viksit Bharat by 2047. Viksit Bharat is a vision for India's future, aiming for inclusive growth, sustainable development, and socio-economic empowerment. However, it faces a no. of challenges, including employment, inflation, and less investment in education. The transition towards formal employment is crucial for reducing income inequality and ensuring widespread prosperity. The GDP metric is limited, and a nuanced approach is needed to account for informal contributions. Addressing inflation requires a multifaceted approach, including prudent monetary policy, supply chain management, and targeted interventions. Holistic policy interventions, such as fostering entrepreneurship, skill development, and innovation, can unlock India's potential and spur economic growth. And by empowering Indian citizens and investing in people-centric growth, India can truly become a developed nation that offers prosperity, dignity and opportunity to all.

References

1. "Budget 2024: What Is 'Viksit Bharat', a Govt Vision to Be Realised by 2047?" 2024. The Indian Express. February 1, 2024.

<https://indianexpress.com/article/what-is/what-is-viksit-bharat-budget-target-2047-nirmala-sitharaman9138965/>.

2. Patel, V., and Kumar, R. (2024). Viksit Bharat 2047: A Journey Towards India's Future. *ShodhKosh: Journal of Visual and Performing Arts*, 5(1), 943–949. doi: 10.29121/shodhkosh.v5.i1.2024.3852
3. Sahoo Jayaparada And Dr. Vadranam Suresh (2024) “Viksit Bharat @2047 Transformation of Society: Vision And Accomplishments” *International Journal of Political and Governance* Volume 6(1) P 79-83.
4. Bhattacharya, Satya Sundar. 2023. “Viksit Bharat@2047: A Visionary Dream or an Unassailable Reality?” *The Times of India*, December 11, 2023. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/blogs/diaries-of-a-lonesome-wonderer/viksitbharat2047-a-visionary-dream-or-an-unassailable-reality/>
5. Viksit Bharat @ 2047(A Blueprint of Micro and Macro Economic Dynamics) By PHD Chamber of Commerce And Industry Voice of Industry And Trade April 2024.
